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ORIGINAL RESEARCH

COMPARISON OF THE RELATIVE STRENGTH AMONG THE DIFFERENT WEIGHT CATEGORIES OF POWER LIFTERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to compare the relative strength among the different weight categories of power lifters. The subjects were selected from the male lifters of All India Inter University Power Lifting Championship held at Lakshmbai National Institute of Physical Education, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh (India). Fifty four (54) male Power lifters were divided into three groups of Eighteen (18) each and the best six (6) in each weight categories was selected as the subject for the study. The Power lifting performance or scores in respective body weight were presented to compare the relative strength among the different weight categories of power lifters. The relative strength of power lifters can be obtained by dividing recorded performance or score with body weight of the subjects. To see the significant difference of relative strength among the different weight categories of power lifters the analysis of variance “F-ratio” was applied at.05 level of significance. For further analysis “Post-Hoc Test” (LSD Test) was applied. The obtained value of “F-ratio” (37.974) was greater than the tabulated value (3.18). The analysis of data reveals that there is a significant difference in the entire three groups in their relative strength, however group I had shown highest relative strength as its mean value is highest among all groups.

Keywords: Relative strength, Body weight, Lifting score, Power lifters

INTRODUCTION

Today is an era of minimum input and maximum output and for this; every possible work is being done to increase efficiency. Every perspective angle is being thoroughly scrutinized by researchers and scientists together, so that sportsman can get maximum mechanical advantage to improve their performance, clear insight of sports during Greek period was reflected in the epic period of Homer. Games were the part of the daily life of the people or any important event.¹ Sports can improve the components of fitness namely: Strength, speed, endurance, flexibility and suppleness. Strength, the ability to exert muscular force is a component of physical fitness and has been of interest since antiquity and many account of super human quality to lift stupendous weight have been recorded. The scientific principles of increasing the load of resistance against which muscles work that strength increases has been called progressive exercise and has been employed extensively in modern times by individuals interested in strength development and athletic performance.² Research indicates that for untrained individual not engaged in heavy manual labor or exercise, maximum muscles strength is reached between the ages of eighteen and twenty, after which it decreases gradually. With increased age and disuse of muscle there can be marked reduction in muscular strength.³ Strength is also one of key to success in modern games and sports. Such as a statement may sound extreme but nevertheless it is true strength, however is the key element because it is more improved than other elements? It is in fact the only element that can only be

improved with one hundred percent success.⁴ Strength training is not only limited to competitive sports, but also training for prevention and rehabilitation, as well as strength training as a leisure time activity in gym is now quite common, strength training was, and still is a major part of athletic training with the aim to improve performance.⁵ Power lifting consists of three separate lifts; the squat, bench press and dead lift. In competitions people are grouped into weight classes where they compete against people of similar weight. Each lifter is allowed 3 attempts in each lift to lift the most weight they can. In order for a lift to be considered “good” at least two of three judges must agree that it was “good” lift, meeting all the rules of the power lifting competition for that lift.⁶

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

The objective of the study is to examine the comparison of relative strength among the different weight categories of power lifters.

METHODS

SUBJECTS

The subjects were selected from the male lifters of All India Inter University Power Lifting Championship held at Lakshmibai National Institute of Physical Education, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh (India). Fifty four (54) male Power lifters were divided into three groups of Eighteen (18) each and the best six (6) in each weight categories was selected as the subject for the study.

CRITERION MEASURE AND RELIABILITY OF DATA

Criterion measure for this study was to compare the power lifting performance or score in the respective body weight categories in All India Inter University Power Lifting Championship for the year 2006-2007. The reliability of data was ensured by establishing the instrument reliability and testers competence. All the instruments and equipments like weighing machine, bar, weight plates, collars, squat stands, benches and outfits were taken from Lakshmibai National Institute of Physical Education, Gwalior, research block and weight training hall, which has been supplied by well know standard agencies and companies. Before the use of these instruments and equipments, they were calibrated for the accurate result. Since the data's for the study is taken from the performance of “All India Inter University Power Lifting Championship” which was held at L.N.I.P.E., Gwalior and was conducted by the qualified National and International referees, these scores were assumed to have higher level of reliability.

PROCEDURE FOR COLLECTION OF DATA

The comparison of relative strength of various lifters of different group, the data was collected from the results of “All India Inter University Power Lifting Championship”. The sum of the best 3 lift of respective events was considered as the scores of the lifters.

PROCEDURE FOR ADMINISTRATION OF TEST

The procedure for administration of the test only nine (9) categories of actual eleven (11) body weight categories was taken by eliminating the first and last two categories i.e. up to 52 kilograms and + 125 kilogram category for relative strength of power lifters. The score or performance achieved in the power lifting namely: Snatch, Bench press and dead lift by the subjects can be divided with the body weight. The relative strength was recorded in kilograms. The scores or performance of the lifters were analyzed by calculating the means and the data were subject to one way analysis of variance in order to find out the significance difference in the means. It was assess by conducting the test in institute laboratory by skilful and specialized experts with use of highly technological instruments.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE EMPLOYED FOR ANALYSIS

To see the significant difference of relative strength among the different weight categories of Power lifters. The analysis of variance “F-ratio” was applied at.05 level of significance. For further analysis “Post-Hoc Test” (LSD Test) was applied.

FINDING

Findings pertaining to relative strength of the different weight categories of power lifters 54 subjects were divided into three groups of 18 each. The sum of the best 3 lifts of respective events was considered as the scores of the lifters. The mean values of all the three groups are having been presented in the following tables 1.

TABLE-1
MEAN OF SCORES OF THE RELATIVE STRENGTH OF LIFTERS FROM DIFFERENT BODY WEIGHT GROUPS

S.NO	GROUP	MEAN(M)
1	I	8.998
2	II	8.038
3	III	6.261

M = Mean value of relative strength in kilograms.

The data were further subjected to one way analysis of variance. The results of one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) of the data of subjects in relative strength are presented in table 2.

TABLE-2
ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE (ANOVA) FOR THE DATA OF RELATIVE STRENGTH OF VARIOUS DIFFERENT CATEGORIES OF POWER LIFTERS

Source of variation	Sum of squares	D.F.	Mean square
Between groups (influence factor)	69.5714	2	34.7857
Within groups (other fluctuations)	46.5370	51	0.9125
Total	116.1084	53	
F-ratio		38.122	
Significance level		P < 0.001	
Factor	N	Mean	Different (P<0.05) from factor nr
(1) 1	18	8.9988	(2)(3)
(2) 2	18	8.0380	(1)(3)
(3) 3	18	6.2589	(1)(2)

Tab. F.05 (2, 51) = 3.18

TABLE-3
PAIRED MEAN DIFFERENCES OF RELATIVE STRENGTH OF VARIOUS DIFFERENT CATEGORIES OF POWER LIFTERS

As shown in Table 2 that the obtained value of 'F' ratio that is 38.122 was greater than the tabulated value of 3.18 for the selected degree of freedom and level of significance which indicates that the subjects of the

entire group differ significantly in relative strength. To further analyses which group is better! Pair wise mean comparison analysis was done by using Post Hoc Test.

TABLE-4
POST HOC TEST FOR THE COMPARISON OF RELATIVE STRENGTH AMONG THE DIFFERENT WEIGHT CATOGARIES OF POWER LIFTERS

MEAN OF DIFFERENT GROUP			MEAN DIFFERENCE	CRITICAL DIFFERENCE
I	II	III		
8.998	8.038		0.960	0.637
8.998		6.261	2.737	
	8.038	6.261	1.777	

Above Table 4 indicate that there were significant differences in the entire three groups.

TABLE-5
POST HOC TEST FOR THE COMPARISON OF RELATIVE STRENGTH AMONG THE DIFFERENT WEIGHT CATOGARIES OF POWER LIFTERS

After applying the Post Hoc Test it was found that there was significant difference in the entire three groups in their relative strength. However group I had higher relative strength.

DISCUSSION OF FINDING

The analysis of data reveals that there is a significant difference in relative strength of various categories of lifters was found at the selected level of significance which establishes that various categories of lifters possesses different level of relative strength. After applying the Post Hoc Test it was found that there was significance difference in groups I (8.998), Group II (8.038) and Group III (6.261) in their relative strength. However group I had higher relative strength. This may be due to the different nature training and pre-requisite components for lifters. Such results may be due to small size of sample and factors such as different body types, difference in the body compositions etc.

The significant differences in relative strength of different weight categories of power lifters were probably due to the different nature of training and pre-requisite components for athletes. Such results may be due to small size of sample and other factors such as different body type, difference in the body composition etc.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study was to compare the relative strength of the power lifters belonging to various categories. Fifty four male lifters who have participated in various categories in All India Inter University Power Lifting Championship held at Lakshmibai National Institute of Physical Education, Gwalior for the year 2006-07 were selected as subjects. Their relative strength was recorded in kilograms. The scores or performance of the lifters were analyzed by calculating the means and the data were subject to one way analysis of variance in order to find out the significance difference in the means. The results have shown that the lifters participated in various categories differ significantly in their relative strength. The selected level of significance was 0.05. After

applying the Post Hoc Test it was observed that there were significant difference in relative strength, however group I (8.998) had highest relative strength as its mean value is highest among all group. The lifters participated in various categories showed a significant difference in their relative strength. Group I had the highest relative strength and its mean value is highest among all the groups.

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